

Using Artificial Intelligence in the Education System

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Abstract. *This article examines the positive and negative consequences of using artificial intelligence in education, discusses the emergence, development, and potential of artificial intelligence systems in the field of education, and discusses ways to improve the quality of education through their application in the educational process.*

Key words: *education, skills, information, process, program, digital science, new, technologies digital technology, intelligence, mind, artificial intelligence, modern education.*

Introduction.

Today, great attention is paid to the education sector in our country. The work being carried out to reform this system is also significant. We can find evidence of these thoughts in the work being carried out to introduce opportunities for the use of modern technologies in this system, to adapt the education system to high and modern requirements. The development and implementation of artificial intelligence (AI) applications for secondary and higher education has the potential to positively change the way students learn subjects and the teaching methods of teachers. AI applications can provide a personalized learning experience for students and offer innovative solutions to problems in the field of education [1].

Materials.

The ideal property of artificial intelligence is the ability to evaluate and implement actions that have the best chance of achieving a specific goal. Currently, artificial intelligence consists of algorithms and software systems designed to perform various actions and can perform a number of tasks that the human mind can perform [2]. The introduction of artificial intelligence and computer technologies into the field of education is becoming a requirement of the modernizing world. The transfer of education to numbers will certainly gain importance in the development of this field. The benefits of using artificial intelligence in education include:

- Helping to further improve the quality of education by saving the time of students and teachers.
- Increasing the level of student mastery
- The ability of the teacher to create new methods using SI and use it in the educational process
- Using various animations and visual aids
- Organizing the lesson process based on the interests of students.
- It provides many benefits, such as increasing the student's individual learning potential and helping to reinforce the knowledge they have learned.

Research and methods.

AI-powered programs can provide useful feedback to students and teachers. AI can not only help academics and students create courses tailored to their preferences, but it can also provide feedback to everyone about the success of the course as a whole. These types of AI systems can help students support themselves and professors look for areas where they can improve their teaching.

There will always be work for teachers in education, but what that role is and what it entails is likely to change as new technologies like intelligent computing systems emerge. As we've discussed, AI taking over tasks like assessment could help students improve their learning and even replace real tutoring.

The World Economic Forum estimates that a significant portion of firms could adopt technologies such as machine learning, thus providing a strong incentive for governments and education to focus on accelerating education and skills development, with a focus on both STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) and non-cognitive soft skills, to fully meet the need at hand. A recent study by Microsoft suggests that by 2030, students could be forced to master two aspects of this new world when they graduate:

- Know how to use changing technologies like artificial intelligence to your advantage;
- Understand how to work with people in a team to effectively solve problems.

Preparing students for the future of AI starts early. Most young people are unfamiliar with digital technologies when they reach college age, so it is crucial to teach them the skills they will need to thrive in digital work. Integrate AI into education, and the long-term force will be ready to face the unknown challenges of tomorrow.

Result and discussion.

In our country, great strides have been made in science and technology, and life itself shows that great results can be achieved in socio-economic areas through the use of digital technologies in every field.

Artificial intelligence continues to transform education today in the form of the following processes:

- in the process of globalization and scientific and technological progress, the importance of artificial intelligence in the education system is increasing;
- through testing and assessment systems, new measurements and criteria can be created for students and pupils using artificial intelligence;
- opportunities for more effective and widespread use of differentiated and individualized education have been created;
- feedback, which plays a very important role in education, can be automated in accordance with the needs of students with artificial intelligence.

In conclusion, artificial intelligence can effectively help students and teachers use innovative teaching methods, develop educational materials, enhance individual learning experiences, and improve the quality of education.

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